

Condensation of Adipyl Chloride with Phenols and Phenolic Ethers

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Adipyl chloride like glutaryl chloride has been condensed with phenol, anisole, *o*- and *m*-cresols and their methyl ethers in presence of aluminium chloride forming exclusively β -(*p*-hydroxy- or *p*-methoxy-benzoyl) valeric acids with traces of diketones. But *p*-cresol, *p*-chlorophenol, and 2-chloro-3-hydroxytoluene afford aryloxy-esters under identical conditions.

In earlier paper Chakravarti and Roy¹ have shown that glutaryl chloride, when condensed with free phenols, provides mainly *p*-hydroxyketo-acids in high yields. In the present communication, the authors have described the condensation of adipyl chloride with phenols and phenolic ethers.

Fuson and Walker² reported that adipyl chloride reacted with benzene, yielding 1,4-dibenzoylbutane (I: R = R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = H).

The ester-acid chloride of adipic acid was used by Papa *et al.*³ in the Friedel-Crafts reaction. Ethyladipyl chloride reacted with benzene in presence of aluminium chloride to furnish δ -benzoylvalerate⁴. Phenol and anisole reacted with methyladipyl chloride to provide δ -(*p*-hydroxybenzoyl)valerate⁵ and δ -(*p*-methoxybenzoyl)valerate respectively.

The reactions between adipyl chloride and phenols or phenolic ethers have not been reported in literature. In this reaction the acyl group in the keto-acids has been found to enter the *p*-position to the hydroxyl group. Phenol, anisole, *o*- and *m*-cresols, and their methyl ethers condense with adipyl chloride, forming δ -(*p*-hydroxy- or methoxy-benzoyl)-

1. *This Journal*, 1965, 42, 607.
2. "Org. Synthesis", 1955, Vol. 13, pp. 32-34.
3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 3018.
4. Grattan, *Compt. rend.*, 1930, 191, 947.
5. Pratt *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1948, 13, 575.

valeric acids(II) and traces of diketones in some cases. But *p*-cresol, *p*-chlorophenol, and 2-chloro-5-hydroxytoluene form aryloxy-esters (III) as the *p*-position is blocked.

The keto-acids on Clemmenson reduction under identical conditions provide the respective caproic acids, having the general formula(IV).

(II)

(III)

(IV)

EXPERIMENTAL

***δ*-(*p*-Hydroxybenzoyl)valeric Acid** (II: $R_1 = \text{OH}$; $R = R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$).—To a stirred and cooled ($0-5^\circ$) mixture of a solution of freshly distilled phenol (2.4 g.) in nitrobenzene (20 ml) and aluminium chloride (7.5 g.) was added dropwise a solution of adipyl chloride (4.6 g.) in nitrobenzene (5 ml) during 30 min. It was then kept at the room temperature for 12 hr. After decomposing by ice and HCl, it was distilled in steam to remove nitrobenzene. The crude product solidified on cooling. It was then treated with Na_2CO_3 solution, filtered, and acidified to yield *δ*-(*p*-hydroxybenzoyl)valeric acid. It was crystallised from hot water in needles, m.p. 150° , yield 2 g. There was no depression in m.p. on admixture with the compound prepared by the method of Pratt *et al.*⁵ (Found: C, 64.65; H, 6.21. Calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$: C, 64.86; H, 6.30%). 2,4-DNP, prepared in the usual way, was crystallised from dilute ethanol in red prisms, m.p. 166° . (Found: N, 13.65. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_7\text{N}_4$ requires N, 13.93%)

The compounds prepared with other phenols and phenolic ethers are described in Table I.

***Di*-(*p*-chlorophenyl)adipate** (III: $R_1 = \text{Cl}$; $R = \text{H}$) was prepared by condensing *p*-chlorophenol (3.2 g.) with adipyl chloride (4.6 g.) in presence of AlCl_3 (7.5 g.) at 0° in nitrobenzene. The product isolated in the usual way was insoluble in Na_2CO_3 or NaOH solution. The crude product was crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 115° . (Found: C, 58.62; H, 4.23. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2$ requires C, 58.85; H, 4.35%.)

When a mixture of *p*-chlorophenol and adipyl chloride was heated in a water bath for 3 hr., it afforded an ester, m.p. 115° . No depression in mixed m.p. with the compound, prepared as above, was observed.

TABLE I
Condensation of phenols and phenolic ethers with adipyl chloride.

Phenol and pheno- lic ethers.	Product formed.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.	Derivative.	Chlammann reduc- tion product.	Remark.
Acetic (in nitro- benzene and tet- rachloroethane, 1:2 at 0°.	(a) β -(<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzoyl)- valeric acid; m.p. 129° (hot water) (lit. m.p. 128°), yield 45%.	[II: R ₁ =OMe; R ₂ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H] C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₄	C: 65.92% H: 6.58	66.10% 6.77	2, 4-DNP; m.p. 165° (EtOH). (Found: N, 13.19. C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₇ N ₄ requires N, 13.46%).		No colour with FeCl ₃ solution.
<i>o</i> -Cresol (in nitro- benzene) at 0°	(b) Insoluble in Na ₂ CO ₃ ; 1,6-Bis-(4-methoxyphenyl)- benzene diene; m.p. 145° (dil. ethanol) (lit. m.p. 144°), yield 55%.	[I: R ₁ =OMe; R ₂ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H] C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₄	C: 73.48 H: 6.52	73.61 6.74	Onim, m.p. 175° (dil. EtOH). (Found: N, 7.32. C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₂ requires N, 7.86%).		Do. This on methylation gave a product iden- tical with the dike- tone obtained from <i>o</i> -cresol methyl ether and adipyl chloride (mixed m.p. 160°).
<i>o</i> -Cresol methyl ether (in nitro- benzene and tet- rachloroethane, 1:1 at 0°.	(a) β -(<i>p</i> -Hydroxy- <i>m</i> -tolyl)- valeric acid; m.p. 123° (hot water), yield 90%.	[II: R ₁ =Me; R ₂ =OH; R ₃ =R ₄ =H] C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₄	C: 65.82 H: 6.45	66.10 6.77	2, 4-DNP, m.p. 162° (EtAc). (Found: N, 12.79. C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₇ N ₄ requires N, 13.02%).	ω -(<i>p</i> -Methoxy- <i>m</i> - methyl phenyl)- caproic acid (IV), R ₁ =Me; R ₂ =OMe R ₃ =R ₄ =H. B.P. 140° 0.3 mm. (Found: C, 70.82; H, 8.21. C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₄ requires C, 71.16; H, 8.47%).	Demethylation of the methyl ether gave β -(<i>p</i> -hydroxy- <i>m</i> -tolyl) valeric acid (mixed m.p. 125°)
<i>o</i> -Cresol methyl ether (in nitro- benzene and tet- rachloroethane, 1:1 at 0°.	(b) Insoluble in Na ₂ CO ₃ ; 1,6- Bis-(4-hydroxy-3 methyl- phenyl) hexane diene; m.p. 204° (dil. ethanol), yield 10%.	[I: R ₁ =OH; R ₂ =Me; R ₃ =R ₄ =H] C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₄	C: 73.27 H: 6.67	73.61 6.74	2, 4-DNP, m.p. 162° (EtAc). (Found: N, 12.79. C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₇ N ₄ requires N, 13.02%).		Do. This on methylation gave a product iden- tical with the dike- tone obtained from <i>o</i> -cresol methyl ether and adipyl chloride (mixed m.p. 160°).
<i>o</i> -Cresol methyl ether (in nitro- benzene and tet- rachloroethane, 1:1 at 0°.	(a) β -(<i>p</i> -Methoxy- <i>m</i> -tolyl)- valeric acid; m.p. 95° (dil. ethanol).	[II: R ₁ =Me; R ₂ =OMe; R ₃ =R ₄ =H] C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₄	C: 66.92 H: 7.00	67.20 7.20	2, 4-DNP, m.p. 162° (EtAc). (Found: N, 12.79. C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₇ N ₄ requires N, 13.02%).	ω -(<i>p</i> -Methoxy- <i>m</i> - methyl phenyl)- caproic acid (IV), R ₁ =Me; R ₂ =OMe R ₃ =R ₄ =H. B.P. 140° 0.3 mm. (Found: C, 70.82; H, 8.21. C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₄ requires C, 71.16; H, 8.47%).	Demethylation of the methyl ether gave β -(<i>p</i> -hydroxy- <i>m</i> -tolyl) valeric acid (mixed m.p. 125°)

TABLE I (contd.)

Phenol and phenolic ether	Product formed.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.	Derivative.	Clemmensen reduction product	Remark.
<i>m</i> -Cresol methyl ether	(<i>b</i>) <i>Isobutals</i> in Na_2CO_3 : 1,6-Bis-(4-methoxy-3-methylphenyl) hexane dione; m.p. 160° (acetic acid).	[I: $\text{R}_2 = \text{OMe}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{Me}$; $\text{R}_3 = \text{H}$] $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4$	C: 74.29% H: 7.18	74.57% 7.34	<i>Osime</i> , m.p. 185° (Found: N, 6.88, $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires N, 7.29%).		
<i>m</i> -Cresol (in nitrobenzene) at 0°	(<i>a</i>) <i>δ</i> -(<i>p</i> -Hydroxy- <i>o</i> -tolyl)-valeric acid; m.p. 100° (hot water).	[II: $\text{R}_2 = \text{Me}$; $\text{R}_2 = \text{OH}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$] $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$	C: 65.78 H: 6.51	66.10 6.77	2,4- <i>DMP</i> , m.p. 185° (EtOH/EtAc) (Found: N, 13.21, $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires N, 13.46%).		Negative ferric reaction
	(<i>b</i>) <i>Isobutals</i> in Na_2CO_3 : 1,6-Bis-(4-hydroxy-2-methylphenyl) hexane dione; m.p. 114° (EtOH).	[I: $\text{R}_2 = \text{OH}$; $\text{R}_2 = \text{Me}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$] $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4$	C: 73.22 H: 6.62	73.61 6.74	<i>Osime</i> , m.p. 131° (dil. EtOH). (Found: N, 7.53, $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires N, 7.86%).		Do On methylation gave a product identical with the diketone obtained from <i>m</i> -cresol methyl ether and adipyl chloride (mixed m.p. 130°).
<i>m</i> -Cresol methyl ether (in nitrobenzene and tetrachloroethane (1:1) at 0°	(<i>a</i>) <i>δ</i> -(<i>p</i> -Methoxy- <i>o</i> -tolyl)-valeric acid; b.p. 160°/0.2 mm.	[II: $\text{R}_2 = \text{Me}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{OMe}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$] $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$	C: 67.00 H: 6.95	67.20 7.20	2,4- <i>DMP</i> , m.p. 173° (ethanol/ethyl acetate) (Found: N, 12.85, $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires N, 13.02%).	<i>o</i> -(<i>p</i> -Methoxy- <i>o</i> -methyl phenyl) caproic acid (IV: $\text{R} = \text{Me}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_2 = \text{OMe}$), b.p. 135°/0.9 mm (mixed m.p. 100°).	Demethylation of the methoxy keto-acid gave <i>δ</i> -(<i>p</i> -hydroxy- <i>o</i> -tolyl) valeric acid (mixed m.p. 100°).
	(<i>b</i>) <i>Isobutals</i> in Na_2CO_3 : 1,6-Bis-(4-methoxy-2-methylphenyl) hexane dione; m.p. 150° (dil. ethanol).	[I: $\text{R}_2 = \text{OMe}$; $\text{R}_2 = \text{Me}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$] $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_4$	C: 74.34 H: 7.08	74.57 7.34	<i>Osime</i> , m.p. 145° (dil. ethanol). (Found: N, 6.92, $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires N, 7.29%).	(Found: C, 70.90; H, 8.15, $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 71.18; H, 8.47%).	

Di-(p-toluyI)adipate (III: $R_1 = \text{Me}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$) was prepared by the same procedure and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 102° (lit. m.p. 99°), yield 80%. (Found: C, 73.63; H, 6.64. Calc. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4$: C, 73.6; H, 6.7%).

Di-(3-methyl-4-chlorophenyl) adipate (III: $R_1 = \text{Me}$; $R_2 = \text{Cl}$) was prepared in the above procedure and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 114° , yield 80%. (Found: C, 60.62; H, 4.94. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2$ requires C, 60.76; H, 5.06%).

2-Chloro-5-hydroxytoluene and adipyl chloride, when refluxed in a water bath for 3 hr., furnished the ester, m.p. 114° ; no depression in mixed m.p. with the compound prepared as above.

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